

A Study on the Challenges Faced By the Startup Ventures in Coimbatore

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Abstract

This study aims to identify and analyze the key challenges faced by startup ventures in Coimbatore, a thriving industrial city in Tamil Nadu, India. The research explores various factors that impact the growth and success of startups, including access to capital, market competition, talent acquisition, government policies, and infrastructure support. By understanding these challenges, policymakers, investors, and entrepreneurs can develop strategies to overcome the barriers and create a conducive ecosystem for startup growth in Coimbatore. The study utilizes a combination of primary data collection through surveys and interviews with startup founders, as well as secondary data from academic research, reports, and industry publications. The Indian economy is based on the monetary policy levied by the central bank of India and the others banks revolve around it. The economy is flourished because of the services provided by the banks and other financial organizations. In the financial organization, the role of banks in providing loans for the need in terms of studies, housing, vehicle, mortgage, pledge, business loans, etc., forms a major part of its services to the customers. The government of India has invested a huge amount of finance in the development of entrepreneurs for the development of rural and urban areas and to increase the employment opportunities of the educated unemployed. In this context, start up ventures provides upliftment of themselves and their families, in addition to society. But the youth are deprived of the rights and support from their family members. The banks play a vital role in bringing startup ventures for the well-being of society. The government of India has introduced lots of schemes for supporting start ups businesses through the banks. The researcher has taken 150 sample startup ventures for studying the problems faced by the startup ventures.

Keywords: startup ventures, financial support, family support, and Government schemes.

Introduction:

Startup ecosystems refer to the interconnected network of resources, institutions, and individuals that support the growth and success of startups in a specific region or industry. These ecosystems provide an environment where entrepreneurs, investors, mentors, and service providers can collaborate and thrive. While startup ecosystems can vary significantly depending on the location and industry focus, they typically consist of the following elements:

1.Talent pool: A vibrant startup ecosystem requires access to a diverse pool of skilled professionals, including entrepreneurs, engineers, designers, marketers, and other specialists. Universities, research institutions, and a culture of innovation play a crucial role in nurturing and attracting talent.

2.Funding sources: Access to capital is essential for startups to grow and scale their operations. Startup ecosystems usually have a range of funding options, including angel investors, venture capitalists, government grants, and crowdfunding platforms. The presence of active and experienced investors willing to take risks on early-stage companies is crucial for ecosystem development.

3.Supportive infrastructure: Startup-friendly infrastructure is necessary to provide entrepreneurs

with the physical and technological resources they need. This includes co-working spaces, incubators, accelerators, maker spaces, and access to excellent-speed internet and other relevant technologies.

4.Mentorship and networking: Experienced mentors and advisors play a vital role in guiding entrepreneurs through the challenges of starting and growing a business. Ecosystems foster networking events, workshops, conferences, and mentorship programs to facilitate knowledge-sharing and relationship-building among entrepreneurs, investors, and industry experts.

5.Regulatory environment: Favorable regulatory frameworks, including business registration processes, intellectual property protection, and tax policies, can significantly impact the growth of startup ecosystems. Governments and policymakers need to create an environment that encourages entrepreneurship and innovation while addressing legal and compliance requirements.

India is a developing country and all the people are not properly employed because of the huge growing population. The government tries to make all the people employed to eradicate poverty in the country. The schemes have not properly reached the people and a few were informed by certain sources, The government has been funding through various

sources and the banks are the means through which the young entrepreneurs are encouraged and financed to start up the business. When coming to youth in India, most of them are not encouraged by any of their family members, peer team, friends, or society. The socio-economic system pushes them from initiating any ideas. Not only in India, but the start-up by youth all around the world also is not as easy as they think.,. But now the education and the confidence in them have made the youth to take up new ideas for starting a business. The education, skill, and knowledge along with adaptability and acceptability have brought up many startup ventures in various fields of big ventures in India. Presently youth in the field of large and small-scale businesses are very less but the number of youth who do business of their own has increased abundantly, though they face many obstacles like strict cultural constraints, limited time, and lack of capital. The study focused on the bank's role in empowering the youth who have a budding idea of starting businesses.

Review of literature

The literature review focuses on the problems faced by startup ventures and the role of banks in granting and supporting the entrepreneurs. The emergence and growth of businesses have significantly aided India's economic growth and development. The majority of businesses in our country are in the service sector. Startup ventures have not only contributed to economic development but have also provided employment opportunities, particularly for youth job seekers. However, it should be noted that entrepreneurs face numerous challenges, particularly in terms of fund generation. An entrepreneur should have a good source of financial knowledge. Finance is the backbone or lifeblood of any company or organization and a lack of adequate financial support makes it difficult to carry on business operations (Mohd Iqbal Dar, 2021). Youth account for nearly 45 percent of the Indian population. At this point, effective steps must be taken to provide youth with entrepreneurial awareness, orientation, and skill development programmes (Deepa S, 2014). The difficulties encountered by entrepreneurs in obtaining loans for their businesses, as well as the difficulties encountered by banks in granting loans, as well as their contribution to entrepreneurship in India (Sushmitha et al., 2018).

Statement of the problem

Youth in India are deprived of their rights in entering any new business by various forces starting from the family to the societal barriers. Youth in the 21st century do not want to refrain from their lives within a small circle of family. The youth has to strive for getting everything in their lives. When a man wants to improve her financial

status and prove herself in society, they have to be educated, improve her skills or start a business. Starting a business calls for a small or large capital. People arrange finance from their sources, borrow from their relatives, and friends, and approach the s for financial support. The banks also provide loans for youth at a concessional rate. The government has also introduced schemes for the development of startup ventures. This is provided through the banks available in India.

Objectives of the study

The following are the aims of the study.

1. To present the socio-economic profile of the start up entrepreneurs.
2. To find the relationship between the socio-economic profile and problems faced by start up ventures.
3. To study the problems faced by start up ventures in starting and raising capital for the business.
4. To study the role of banks in the development of start up ventures in India.

Scope of the study

The researcher tries to reveal the unknown government schemes introduced for the startup ventures and the huge investment that has been made for the empowerment of the entrepreneurs in India. For the study, the researcher has taken 150 start up ventures and adopted a convenience sampling method. The study would bring out the empowerment schemes that would help budding startup ventures.

Problems faced by startup ventures in India

1. Funding are some of the hurdles faced by startup ventures while having an idea of starting a business. Lack of funding: Access to capital remains a significant challenge, particularly for early-stage startups or those operating in regions with limited investment opportunities. Startups may struggle to secure funding due to risk aversion among investors, limited local investment networks, or inadequate government support.
2. Talent retention: Competition for skilled professionals is fierce, and startups often find it challenging to attract and retain top talent. Established companies and larger organizations may offer more attractive compensation packages and stability, making it difficult for startups to compete.
3. Regulatory barriers: Excessive bureaucracy, complex regulations, and legal hurdles can stifle innovation and hinder startup growth. Outdated or restrictive policies may discourage entrepreneurship and create unnecessary burdens for startups, especially in excellently regulated industries.
4. Limited market size: Some startup ecosystems may face challenges due to small local markets or limited customer bases. Startups in such regions often need to expand to larger markets or adapt their

business models to operate globally, which can be a complex and resource-intensive process.

5. Lack of entrepreneurial culture: Developing a strong entrepreneurial mindset and culture takes time and effort. Some regions may lack a supportive culture that encourages risk-taking, embraces failure as a learning opportunity, and celebrates entrepreneurial success. Building an ecosystem with a thriving entrepreneurial spirit requires a collective effort from various stakeholders.

Overcoming these challenges requires collaboration between entrepreneurs, investors, government entities, educational institutions, and the broader

business community. By addressing funding gaps, fostering talent development, creating favorable regulatory environments, and cultivating a supportive culture, startup ecosystems can flourish and drive economic growth.

Analysis and Interpretation

The researcher used percentage analysis and correlation for this study. Percentage analysis was adopted to present the socio-economic profile of the respondents. Correlation was used to find the relationship between socio-economic profile and problems faced by the respondents during their business

Table 1: Age group of the respondents

Sl. No.	Age Group	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 30 years	50	20.00
2	31 years to 45 years	68	27.20
3	Above 45 years	32	12.80
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the age group of the respondents. Out of one hundred and fifty respondents, fifty (20.00%) respondents are less than 30 years old. Sixty-eight (27.20%) respondents are between the age group of 31 years and 45 years and the remaining thirty-two (12.80%) respondents are above 45 years of age. The majority (27.20%) of the respondents are between 31 years and 45 years.

Table 2: Educational qualification of the respondents

Sl.No.	Educational Qualification	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	School level	49	19.60
2	Graduates	68	27.20
3	Others	33	13.20
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the educational qualification of the respondents. Out of one hundred and fifty respondents, forty-nine (19.60%) respondents studied school level. Sixty-eight (27.20%) respondents are graduates and the remaining thirty-three (13.20%) respondents studied other courses. The majority (27.20%) of the respondents are graduates.

Table 3: Family members of the respondents

Sl. No.	Family Members	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 3 members	58	23.20
2	Above 3 members	92	36.80
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the family members of the respondents. Fifty-eight (23.20%) respondents' family members are less than 3 and the remaining ninety-two (36.80%) respondents' family members are above 3. The majority (36.80%) of the respondent's family members are above 3.

Table 4: Family type of the respondents

Sl. No.	Family type	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Nuclear family	56	22.40
2	Joint family	94	37.60
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the family type of the respondents, fifty-six (22.40%) respondents are nuclear families, and the remaining ninety-four (37.60%) respondents are joint families. The majority (37.60%) of the respondents are joint families.

Table 5: Place of Residence of the respondents			
Sl. No.	Place of Residence	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Rural	33	13.20
2	Urban	71	28.40
3	Semi-urban	46	18.40
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the place of residents of the respondents. Thirty-three (13.20%) respondents are residing in rural. Seventy-one (28.40%) respondents are residing in urban and the remaining forty-six (18.40%) respondents are residing in semi-urban areas. The majority (28.40%) of the respondents are residing in urban areas.

Table 6: Business experience of the respondents			
Sl. No.	Business experience	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 5 years	63	25.20
2	6 years to 10 years	51	20.40
3	Above 10 years	36	14.40
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the business experience of the respondents. Sixty-three (25.20%) respondents are having less than 5 years of business experience. Fifty-one (20.40%) respondents are having business experience of 6 years to 10 years and the remaining thirty-six (14.40%) respondents are having 10 years of experience and above. The majority (25.20%) of the respondents are having less than 5 years of experience.

Table 7: Family support to the respondents			
Sl. No.	Family support	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Poor	68	27.20
2	Good	51	20.40
3	Excellent	33	13.20
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the family support of the respondents. Sixty-eight (27.20%) of the respondents are having a poor level of family support. Fifty-one (20.40%) of the respondents are having a good level of family support and the remaining thirty-three (13.20%) of the respondents are having an excellent level of family support. The majority (27.20%) of the respondents are having a good level of family support.

Table 8: Financial support to the respondents			
Sl. No.	Financial support	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Poor	87	34.80
2	Good	45	18.00
3	Excellent	18	7.20
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the financial support of the respondents. Eighty-seven (34.80%) respondents have a poor level of financial support. Forty-five (18.00%) respondents have a good level of financial support and the remaining eighteen (7.20%) respondents have an excellent level of financial support. The majority (34.80%) of the respondents are having a poor level of financial support.

Table 9: Lack of Knowledge in approaching banks of the respondents			
Sl. No.	Lack of Knowledge in approaching banks	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Poor	23	9.20
2	Good	38	15.60
3	Excellent	89	35.60
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the lack of knowledge in approaching banks of the respondents. Twenty-three (9.20%) respondents have a poor level of lack of knowledge in approaching banks. Thirty-eight (15.60%) respondents have a good level of lack of knowledge in approaching banks and the remaining eighty- nine (35.60%) respondents have an excellent level of lack of knowledge in approaching banks. The majority (35.60%) of the respondents are having an excellent level of Lack of Knowledge in approaching banks.

Sl. No.	Unaware of the Government Schemes	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Poor level of awareness	84	33.60
2	Good level of awareness	30	12.00
3	Excellent level of awareness	36	14.40
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the unawareness of the Government scheme of the respondents. Eighty-four(33.60%) respondents have a poor level of awareness. Thirty (12.00%) respondents have a good level of awareness and the remaining thirty- six (14.40%) respondents have an excellent level of awareness of the Government schemes. The majority (33.60%) of the respondents are having an excellent level of awareness of Government scheme

Lack of family support		Lack of financial support	Lack Knowledge of in approaching banks	Unaware of the government schemes
1	Lack of family support			
**0.871	Lack of financial support	1		
0.321	Lack of Knowledge in approaching banks	*0.714	1	
*0.813	Unaware of the government schemes	**0.836	*0.783	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The above table shows the correlation between the variables. Lack of financial support (0.871) has a positive and significant relationship with lack of family support at 1% significant and unaware of government schemes (0.813) has a positive and significant relationship with lack of family support at 5% significant.

Lack of knowledge in approaching banks (0.714) has a positive and significant relationship with lack of financial support at 5% significant level and unaware of the government schemes (0.836) has a positive and significant relationship with lack of financial support at 1% significant level. Lack of knowledge in approaching banks (0.783) has a positive and significant relationship with Unaware of the government schemes at 5% significant level.

Findings

The following are the findings of the study which were taken from the percentage analysis.

1. Majority (27.20%) of the respondents are between 31 years and 45 years.
2. Majority (27.20%) of the respondents are graduates.
3. Majority (36.80%) of the respondent's family members are above 3.
4. Majority (37.60%) of the respondents are joint families.
5. Majority (28.40%) of the respondents are residing in urban areas.
6. Majority (25.20%) of the respondents are having less than 5 years of experience.
7. Majority (27.20%) of the respondents are having a good level of family support.
8. Majority (34.80%) of the respondents are having an excellent level of financial support.
9. Majority (35.60%) of the respondents are having an excellent level of Lack of Knowledge in approaching banks.

10. Majority (33.60%) of the respondents are having an excellent level of awareness of Government schemes.

Suggestions

Folpooring are some of the suggestions for startup ventures and the banks in providing loans for them

1. The person who has the idea of starting a business should gain some knowledge about the schemes available for youth by the government.

2. Start up ventures' idea has to be generated by visiting DIC (District Industrial Centre) and getting support from the DIC officers.

3. Internet provides a lot of information regarding the schemes for startup ventures, the ways of raising funds, what business ideas can be taken, and how to approach the banks for financial support.

4. The banks should make the loan formalities easier for the youth who come with lesser knowledge about the procedures in approaching for loan.

5. The banks should relax the bottleneck conditions in providing funds to the SMEs by the authorities.

6. The assets that are brought as collateral should be properly checked, to make the youth comfortable in paying off the debts.

Conclusion

By conducting this study, we aim to provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by startup ventures in Coimbatore. The findings will serve as a foundation for developing effective strategies to address these challenges and foster a favorable environment for the growth and success of startups. Youth are the eyes of the nation and they could bring light to the family and society by starting a business of their own. A spark in them in starting a business, balancing the family and the business, perfect utilization of the time for the business and family, supporting and uplifting the family resulting in the economic development of the nation. The family members should support them in a way that the youth should be able to concentrate more on the business. Today, we are in a better position because women's participation in the field of entrepreneurship is increasing at a rapid pace. Efforts are being made in the economy to bring Indian youth the promise of equality of opportunity in all spheres, and laws guaranteeing equal rights of participation in the political process, as well as equal opportunities and rights in education and employment, have been enacted. Unfortunately, government-sponsored development activities have benefited only a few. The banks should make a campaign in introducing the new schemes of the government and also in approaching the banks for loans and the settlement of the same. The government schemes and the investment made should properly reach the concerned people in the right manner by the authorities.

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